

METHODOLOGICAL MODEL OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The given scientific work analyzes the methodology for creating a methodological model aimed at developing students' professional competence in higher educational institutions. Students' professional competence has become one of the main goals of higher education today. Improving their professional readiness, adapting to the requirements of the modern labor market, as well as forming the knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for successful future activity play an important role for students in the process of studying. The article deeply studies the main elements of the methodological model, its structure and impact on the educational process.*

Keywords: *professional competence, higher education, methodological model, educational process, students, methodology.*

INTRODUCTION. It is important to suggest that in the world, while training specialists for the modern energy sector, special attention is paid to the formation of their professional competence in this area. The process of formation and development of professional competence of future specialists is carried out in higher education institutions. The system of training students in universities is carried out on the basis of regulatory documents (qualification requirements, curricula, training programs) stipulated by law. In accordance with the curriculum, before studying specialties, students are taught general professional subjects, including electrical engineering.

Definitely, the use of mobile applications along with the use of pedagogical and digital technologies in teaching electrical engineering disciplines not only increases students' interest in science, but also serves to form their professional competence at a high level [1].

However, the development of professional competence in higher education remains a pressing issue in order to ensure the training of highly qualified specialists in accordance with the economic and social needs of society. The educational process requires effective methods and methodological models for guiding students towards professional competence. This work reflects the theoretical foundations of a new methodological model aimed at developing professional competence, its components, methodological methods and issues of integration into the educational process [4].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

It should be mentioned that the analysis of literature is aimed at studying various concepts of professional competence and its impact on the educational process. Many scientific studies have developed pedagogical approaches and methods necessary for the development of professional competence in higher education. Based on the analyzed literature, the importance of integrative and practical approaches in the development of professional competence, as well as the role of modern educational technologies, is especially noted. The research methodology uses a systematic approach, pedagogical experiment, monitoring of the educational process and assessment systems.

Additionally, Yu.A. Eshniyozov in his article "Development of professional competence skills of students in the process of teaching electrical engineering disciplines" believes that it is

advisable to implement professional competence and innovative abilities of students in the process of practical training in electrical engineering disciplines at the following stages.

The first stage is the perception of educational materials. Thus, students become familiar with the content of education and understand what their cognitive tasks are. Such processes as intuition, perception and imagination take an active part in this.

The second stage is when students become aware of the educational material, understand its essence and generalize. As a result, new knowledge is acquired, the ability to analyze, compare and draw conclusions based on their own knowledge is formed.

The third stage is consolidated through new knowledge, projects, independent work, additional comments from the teacher, students are individually given tasks for independent, creative thinking about science (subject).

At the fourth stage, the developments and innovative projects completed by students are considered and analyzed.

At the fifth stage, they apply the acquired knowledge and innovative projects in practice, depending on the opportunity. Thanks to these stages, the teacher can effectively organize and manage the educational process of students. Therefore, at all stages of the educational process, the teacher acts as a leader and guide [2].

What is more interesting, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor I.Kh. Ibragimov in his article "Theoretical Foundations for Improving the Professional Competence of Teachers of Higher Education Institutions" mentioned that in the education system, it is literally possible to systematically convey high-quality, useful, important, necessary, desirable and practical information to modern students. A teacher must be able to quickly receive, process and convey information to students, effectively and interestingly. This determines the need for a teacher to possess the qualities of professional competence, the basics of pedagogical skill, and the ability to be creative. Familiarity with the basics of pedagogical competence, pedagogical skill and creativity of higher education teachers helps them organize the educational process creatively, interestingly and in a student-active manner [3].

RESULTS.

Surprisingly, the creation of a methodological model for the development of professional competence of students of higher educational institutions contributes to the improvement of the efficiency of the educational process. Such a model, in turn, should be aimed at improving the professional training of students, developing their practical skills and forming the competencies necessary for them to work successfully in the labor market. The methodological model aimed at developing professional competence was created using the following steps and approaches (Fig. 1).

1. Theoretical foundations of the model. When creating a model, first of all, it is necessary to define the essence of the concept of professional competence. Professional competence means knowledge, abilities and skills necessary for students to effectively carry out their professional activities [4].

Professional competence:

- Knowledge: deep understanding of the subject area and acquisition of theoretical knowledge.
- Abilities: the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practice.
- Skills: experience and relationships necessary for effectiveness in practice.

2. Modelning asosiy elementlari Kasbiy kompetentlikni rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan metodik model quyidagi asosiy elementlardan tashkil topgan.	1. Modelning nazariy asoslari			4. Metodik usullar va texnologiyalar ni joriy etish Modelni amalda qo'llash uchun samarali metodik usullar va texnologiyalarni belgilash kerak. Jumladan: 4.2. Simulyatsiyalar va case-study metodlari: Talabalarga muammolarni yechishda interaktiv o'yinlar, case-study metodlari va real hayotdan olingan misollar orqali amaliy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish.	
	Kasbiy kompetentlik — bu talabalar tomonidan o'z kasbiy faoliyatini samarali bajarish uchun zarur bo'lgan bilim, ko'nikmalar va malakalarni anglatadi.				
	1.1. Bilim: sohani chuqur tushunish va nazariy bilimlarni egallash.	1.2. Ko'nikmalar: nazariy bilimlarni amaliyotda qo'llash qobiliyati.	1.3. Malakalar: amaliyotda samarali ishlash uchun zarur bo'lgan tajribalar.		
	2.1. Ma'lumot va bilimlar: Talabalarga soha bo'yicha chuqur nazariy bilimlar berish.	3. O'quv jarayonini rejalashtirish Metodik modelni tatbiq etishda o'quv jarayonini aniq rejalashtirish kerak. Bu bosqichda o'quvchilar uchun quyidagilarni hisobga olish muhim:	4.1. Masofaviy ta'lim (elektron ta'lim platformalari): OTMda masofaviy ta'lim kurslarini tashkil etish orqali talabalarni zamonaviy texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish.		
	2.2. Amaliy ko'nikmalar: Talabalarga kasbiy faoliyatda zarur bo'lgan amaliy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish.		4.3. Simulyatsiyalar va case-study metodlari: talabalar o'rtasida guruhli ishlarni tashkil etish, masalalarni birgalikda yechish va fikr almashish.		
	2.3. Innovatsion yondashuvlar: O'quv jarayonida raqamli texnologiyalar va interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish.	3.1. O'quv dasturlari va kurslar: Talabalarga kasbiy kompetentlikni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan kurslar va o'quv dasturlari ishlab chiqish.	5. Baholash va monitoring: Modelning samaradorligini baholash uchun tizimli monitoring va baholash tizimlarini ishlab chiqish zarur. Bu talabalar kasbiy kompetentlik darajasini aniqlash va o'quv jarayonini optimallashtirish uchun muhimdir.		
	2.4. Individual va jamoaviy ishlash: Talabalar o'z bilim va ko'nikmalarini o'zlashtirishda individual va jamoaviy ishlashda o'zlarini sinab ko'rishlari.	3.2. O'quv materiallari: Talabalarga kerakli o'quv materiallari, elektron resurslar, onlayn platformalar va o'quv qo'llanmalarini taqdim etish.			
	2.5. Pedagogik amaliyot va feedback (fikr-mulohazalar): Talabalar amaliyotda kasbiy ko'nikmalarini sinashlari va bu borada doimiy feedback (fikr-mulohazalar) olishlari kerak.				
	5.1. Qisqa va uzun muddatli baholash: Talabalar bilim va ko'nikmalarini turli bosqichlarda (kurs oxirida, amaliyot jarayonida) baholash.		5.2. Feedback tizimi (fikr-mulohazalar): Talabalar tomonidan olingan feedback (fikr-mulohazalar)lar asosida o'quv jarayonini takomillashtirish.		
	6. Tadqiqot va eksperimentlar: Pedagogik tajribasini ishlarida Modelni amaliyotga joriy etish mumkin. Tadqiqotlar natijalari modelning samaradorligi, talabalar kasbiy kompetentligi va o'quv jarayonidagi o'zgarishlarni o'rganish imkonini beradi.		7. Modelni tatbiq etish va takomillashtirish: Modelni joriy etganidan keyin o'quv jarayonining samaradorligini kuzatish, baholash va kerakli o'zgartirishlar kiritish mumkin. Olingan natijalarga asoslanib, metodik modelni takomillashtirish va kelajakda yanada samarali qilish imkonini mavjud.		
8. Xulosa: Talabalar kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan metodik model, o'quv jarayonini yanada samarali qilish va talabalar tayyorgarligini yaxshilashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Metodik modelni yaratish va uning amaliyotda qo'llanilishi, talabalar mehnat bozorida muvaffaqiyatli ishlashiga yordam beradi va ular uchun kasbiy tayyorgarlikni oshirishning yangi imkoniyatlarini yaratadi.					

Figure 1. Methodological model aimed at developing professional competence

The following methodological approaches are used as the basis for creating a methodological model that includes these concepts as a theoretical basis:

- Systematic approach: all elements of the model are interconnected and serve a common purpose.

- Integrated approach: When developing students' professional training, attention is paid not only to knowledge, but also to skills and competencies.

- Practical approach: Methods aimed at the rapid and effective formation of professional skills.

1. Main elements of the methodological model: The methodological model aimed at developing professional competence should consist of the following main elements:

- Information and knowledge: provide students with deep theoretical knowledge in this area.

Acquisition of knowledge through lectures, seminars and practical classes.

- Practical skills: Develop practical skills necessary for students in their professional activities.

Practice, internships, laboratory work, advanced training.

- Innovative approaches: use of modern technologies and interactive methods in the educational process.

-Online courses, simulations and games, case study methods.

- Individual and group work: Students need to test themselves in individual and group work in mastering their knowledge and skills.

Projects, group discussions and problem solving.

- Teaching practice and feedback: Students should test their professional skills in practice and receive constant feedback.

Mentoring, observation, assessment by teachers and specialists.

3. Planning the educational process

While implementing the methodological model, it is necessary to clearly plan the educational process. At this stage, it is important for students to consider the following:

- Educational programs and courses: Develop courses and educational programs aimed at developing students' professional competence.

- Educational materials: Provide students with the necessary educational materials, electronic resources, online platforms and teaching aids.

- Internships and work placements: Organize practical classes and internship programs for students to improve their professional preparedness through practice.

4. Implementation of methods and technologies.

In order to apply the model in practice, it is necessary to identify effective methods and technologies. Including:

- Distance education (e-learning platforms): introduce students to modern technologies by organizing distance learning courses in a higher education institution.

- Modeling and case study methods: develop students' practical problem-solving skills through interactive games, case study methods and real-life examples.

- Collaborative learning: organizing students' group work, joint problem solving and exchange of ideas.

5. Evaluation and monitoring

For evaluating the effectiveness of the model, it is necessary to develop systematic monitoring and evaluation systems. It is important to determine the level of students' professional competence and optimize the learning process. Evaluation methods:

- Short-term and long-term evaluation: Evaluation of students' knowledge and skills at different stages (at the end of the course, during practice).

- Feedback system: improving the learning process based on the feedback received by students.

6. Research and Experiments

Before applying the model in practice, it is necessary to conduct pedagogical experiments. Thanks to research, it is possible to study the effectiveness of the model, professional competence of students and changes in the educational process.

7. Implementation and improvement of the model.

After implementing the model, it is possible to monitor, evaluate the effectiveness of the educational process and make the necessary changes. Based on the results obtained, it is possible to improve the methodological model and make it more effective in the future.

DISCUSSION.

The created methodological model can be effectively used in developing the professional competence of students in the process of higher education. The results of the model implementation allow students to deepen their professional skills and work successfully in practice. Also, the methodological foundations for developing professional competence in educational institutions are important not only for improving pedagogical processes, but also for ensuring the successful work of students in the labor market.

CONCLUSION.

It should be suggested that a methodological model aimed at developing the professional competence of students plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process and improving the training of students. In the process of creating a model, it is necessary to use modern pedagogical approaches, methods for developing practical skills, interactive and innovative technologies. The creation of a methodological model and its application in practice will help students to work successfully in the labor market and will create new opportunities for them to improve their professional training.

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